

Supporting Information

SI Methods

Single channel recording and data analysis. The single channel studies for G551D- and WT-CFTR were performed by using the stably transfected FRT cells, the expression system provided more accurate open probability (P_o) estimates by limiting the number of channels in per patch (41). The P_o was analyzed as previously described (42). In brief, only records that contained fewer than 8 simultaneous openings after VX-770 addition were analyzed by Clampfit. P_o was estimated for each condition by dividing the NP_o product measured for that condition by the maximal number of simultaneous openings observed after VX-770 addition (N). Single channel opening rates (openings/sec) were estimated by dividing openings (total events/2 in each condition) by recording time of each condition. The number of data for different doses of PKA were collected from both the continued series experiments as indicated in S2 A and the experiments of a separated single dose (286 or 572 U/ml) of PKA application.

Fig. S1: PKA dose-dependently increases G551D-CFTR channel activity in the presence of ATP s and a low dose of ATP. A. A macropatch record shows slow activation of G551D-CFTR after adding multiple doses of PKA, while ATP s had no effect on channel activity before adding PKA (n=6). Bath was washed (~2 min) with ATP free solution before recording. VX-770 (200 nM) was added before adding the CFTR inhibitor. B. Protein kinase A inhibitor (PKI) prevent further increase in channel activity that was activated by PKA and ATP s. Inset: an enlarged section between zero time of recording and before adding VX-770 (n=2). C. PKA dose dependently increases channel activity of G551D-CFTR in the presence of a low dose ATP (25 μM , n=2).

Fig. S2: High doses of PKA increase channel open probability (P_o) and opening rate of G551D-CFTR. **A.** Multichannel record for inside-out patch excised from FRT cell stably expressed G551D-CFTR. Control condition was identical to Fig 1 A and B. Additional PKA and 200 nM VX-770 were added where indicated. The holding potential: -60 mV. **B.** Current traces from indicated sections (a, b, c) in panel A. **C.** Comparison of mean P_o (left panel) and opening rate (right panel) between control and high dose of PKA as indicated by circle (control), square (PKA 286 U/ml,) and triangle (PKA 572 U/ml). Bar graphs indicate means and SEM. t-test: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

Fig. S3: High doses of PKA moderately increase channel open probability (P_o) of WT-CFTR. **A.** Multichannel record for inside-out patch excised from FRT cell stably expressed WT-CFTR. Control condition was identical to Fig 1 A and B. Additional PKA and 200 nM VX-770 were added whereindicated. The holding potential: -60 mV. **B.** Current traces from indicated sections (a, b, c) in panel A. **C.** Comparison of mean P_o (left panel) and opening rate (right panel) between control and high dose of PKA as indicated by circle (control), square (PKA 286 U/ml,) and triangle (PKA 572 U/ml) . Bar graphs indicate means and SEM. t-test: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.